

Improving the awareness of mobile malware risks: How does this affect the continuance of mobile payment usage?

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ABSTRACT

The current study explored the effects of increasing risk-awareness concerning mobile malware risks on mobile payment usage in order to shed light on a relatively unexplored field with high theoretical and partly practical relevance. A group of thirty people was assessed to participate in an experiment which existed of an intervention and a survey, before and after the intervention. The results of the experiment concluded that when people are made aware of mobile malware risks their usage of mobile payment systems decreases.

Keywords

Risk-awareness, Mobile payment usage, Mobile Malware risks, Intervention impact.

INTRODUCTION

Mobile payments are the future as we move towards a cashless world. For the past decennium the use of mobile payment emerged in our society, according to PwC (2019) around 51% of the Dutch population is using mobile payment methods. Mobile payment methods such as banking apps, 'Tikkie' or mobile wallets are trending technologies in the Netherlands that facilitate banking transactions at any moment. Mobile payment methods are increasing popularity due to the ease of the technologies; at least 80% of respondents in the Netherlands recognized the benefits of mobile payment: easy payment, immediate monitoring of money movements on your mobile phone and no need to carry cash (PwC, 2019). But they did not only point out the benefits, but also the risks that mobile payment methods carry, 23% of the respondents are concerned about the protection of their data. They stated that they're worried their phone could be stolen and misused to make mobile payments (PwC, 2019). But neither of the respondents claimed to be afraid of digital threats like malware. This is remarkable, since the number

of mobile threats is increasing rapidly; since the beginning of 2016 and the end of 2018, the number of mobile malware attacks increased from 10 million to more than 30 million (McAfee Labs, 2018).

The current study will examine the effects of increasing the risk-awareness of mobile malware risks through an intervention on the continuance of mobile payment usage among university students. It will examine whether increasing the risk-awareness will change the usage continuance of mobile payment systems.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Several studies are conducted concerning risk-awareness and acceptance in the adoption process of mobile payment systems (Ramos de Luna, I., Liébana-Cabanillas, F., Sánchez-Fernández, J. & Muñoz-Leiva, F., 2019; Liébana-Cabanillas, F., Muñoz-Leiva, F. & Sánchez-Fernández, J., 2013). Lack of initial trust is identified as a significant barrier for the adoption of mobile payment systems for mobile users (Zhou, T., 2011; Gao & Waechter, 2017). Zhou (2011) concluded that the perceived security has the strongest effect on initial trust for potential mobile payment users. During the time the respondents choose not to adopt the technology because of the risks they experienced with mobile payment (Zhou, T., 2011; Gao & Waechter, 2017). The perceived risks to a mobile payment platform will reduce the consumers' trust and affect their attitude (Yang, Q., Pang, C., Liu, L., Yen, D. C. & Tarn, J. M., 2015), therefore reducing their intention to use mobile payment systems (Pelaez, A., Chen, C. W., & Chen, Y. X., 2019).

Previous studies in the academic field of mobile payment have mainly focused on the initial adoption and usage of mobile payment but have ignored largely post-adoption usage (Qasim and Abu-Shanab, 2016; Oliveira, T., Thomas, M., Baptista, G. & Campos, F., 2016; Cao, X., Yu, L., Liu, Z., Gong, M. & Adeel, L., 2018). However, post-adoption attitude in mobile payment differs from the pre-adoption attitude. An example of this

difference is the role of trust; trust is a significant factor for the adoption of mobile payment (Zhou, T., 2011; Gao & Waechter, 2017), but trust is not a significant factor for the continuance of mobile payment usage (Liu, Z., Ben, S. & Zhang, R., 2019). Because 51% of the Dutch population have already adopted the technology for mobile payment services (PwC, 2019), it is relevant to investigate the post-adoption usage.

With the emergence of mobile malware threats (McAfee, 2018) there are more threats rising for mobile payment users post-adoption. Since the risks of mobile payment platforms reduced the intention to use mobile payment systems (Pelaez, A. et al. 2019), it is a relevant question to research if the awareness of the risks will influence the continuance intention of mobile payment systems post-adoption.

The users have not yet been exposed to an intervention to promote awareness and reduce risk behaviour concerning mobile payment systems. There is a study about the effect of an intervention on risk-awareness and behavior in a school regarding online environment/internet (Schilder, J. D., Brusselaers, M. B. J. & Bogaerts, S., 2015). This research found a positive relation between an intervention on risk-awareness and online behaviour, which was noticeable till four months later (Schilder et al. 2015). Performing a similar study in the field of mobile payments will increase the knowledge over post-adoption behaviour, which contributes to the knowledge gap that is noticed and mentioned by academics in previous studies (Qasim & Abu-Shanab, 2016; Oliveira et al., 2016; Cao, X. et al., 2018). Moreover, this exploratory research will provide new insights about the role of interventions in the attempt to raise risk-awareness.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The key question of this paper is as follows:

To what extent will an increase in risk-awareness, through an intervention, affect the continuance of mobile payment usage?

In the conceptual model below 'Risk-awareness' is the independent variable. We expect that risk-awareness has an influence on the dependent variable 'Continuance of mobile payment usage' through the mediator being the 'Intervention'.

Table 1. Conceptual Model

Based on the theory and research question the

following hypothesis will be measured:

H1: an increase of risk-awareness of mobile payment risks through an intervention will affect the continuance of mobile payment usage.

Based on the discussed literature, it is expected that an intervention will raise the mobile payment risk-awareness of university students. Besides that, it is also expected that the intervention will change the behaviour of using mobile payment systems in a way that action will be considered before acting.

Literature

To understand the relationship between risk-awareness and the continuance of mobile payment usage, various theories are reviewed and discussed.

Continuance of mobile payment usage

Existing vulnerabilities in mobile payment systems will increase the risk users perceive, which in turn will affect the users continuance usage intention. In order to counteract this phenomenon, users must build trust to increase the continuance of mobile payment usage (Cao, X. et al., 2018). Since the effect on the continuance of mobile payment usage is studied in this paper, the aim of this literature is relevant.

Trust is a reflection of willingness to be vulnerable based on the positive expectation towards another party's future behaviour (Mayer, R.C., Davis, J.H. & Schoorman, F.D., 1995). Based on the theory by Zahedi and Song (2008), trust contains three dimensions: ability, integrity and benevolence. Ability reflects the knowledge and expertise mobile payment systems claim to have to complete their tasks. Integrity relies on mobile payment systems to keep promises and benevolence reflects interest in users by mobile payment systems without the influence of their own benefits.

Trust in online payment methods are a reflection of the beliefs in trustworthiness of online payment methods. Online payment methods have been popular among users. Therefore, if users have developed trust in online payment systems, there is a significant predictor the users continue using mobile payment systems if it belongs to the same brand they have trusted before (Zhou, T., 2014).

Risk-awareness

Several variables play an important role in increasing the risk-awareness. The study 'A survey of Mobile Malware in the Wild' (Porter Felt, A., Finifter, M., Chin, E., Hanna, S. & Wagner, D., 2011) used the mobile threat model which gives three types of threats: malware, grayware and

personal spyware. Malware can be defined as: ‘gains access to a device for the purpose of stealing data, damaging the device, or annoying the user, etc.’ This threat includes Trojans, worms, botnets, and viruses (Porter Felt, A. et al., 2011). Grayware is defined as: ‘spies on users, but the companies that distribute grayware do not aim to harm users’ (Porter Felt, A. et al., 2011). At last, personal spyware can be defined as: ‘the attacker has physical access to the device and installs the software without the user's knowledge’ (Porter Felt, A. et al., 2011). Credential theft, credit card theft via NFC, and advertising click fraud are the most likely to be targeted by future malware authors (Porter Felt, A. et al., 2011). Since the knowledge of the existence of the types of mobile threats, as well as the most threatful ones, is of great importance for setting up the intervention, this study gives a good perspective on this subject.

Intervention

Interventions are commonly used in the health sector, but the study of Schilder et al. (2015) indicates that interventions are also useful for increasing the risk awareness in online behaviour. Since the use of mobile payment systems is a more specific form of online behaviour, using an intervention method is applicable for this research.

According to K. Monsen (2017) using an effective method to measure the intervention is more important than the actual intervention. The effect of the intervention will therefore be measured with the use of a program evaluation, which is a structured process intended to measure whether or not an intervention or program was successful in meeting its goals (K. Monsen, 2017).

METHODOLOGY

In this section the sampling strategy and data gathering method are mentioned as well as the statistical analysis technique.

Sampling strategy

In this section the first four steps (defining the population, defining the sampling frame, determining the sampling design and determine the sample size of the sampling process) are discussed in order to give the final sample.

The population of this research, Dutch people that use mobile payment systems, was a sampling frame that could not be specifically addressed. Because of this ambiguous population the final sample was selected with a convenience sampling technique. The sample consisted of 35 University

students who were between the ages of 19 and 25. This provided a homogeneous sample wherein the respondents had the same educational level and were in the same age range. To increase the validation, all participants within the groups received the same intervention. This study was conducted with thirty convenient selected students from the University of Tilburg. Each student was randomly assigned to one of two different groups.

Experiment

On 11 November, the first survey was sent to collect data of participants' usage of mobile payment systems. This survey was conducted to measure the baseline of the frequency of mobile payment usage and the perception of the risks of mobile payment usage. The survey was spread via WhatsApp groups of different studies at Tilburg University.

Afterwards the respondents were randomly assigned to group one, which was an experimental group, or group two, which was a control group. On November 18th group one received the actual intervention (X1, n=20) and group two (n=10) received a general instruction video.

Participants selected to group 1 received a self-made video instruction where the emerging mobile payment risks were presented. In this video instruction, the risks that Porter Felt (2011) noticed were explained by using the same definitions as the paper. The risks that were instructed were; mobile malware forms, mobile grayware and personal spyware. To improve the relevance of the instruction, a recent example of a mobile scam was included. Since it is a purpose of an intervention to change risky behaviour (Schilder, 2015), practical tips were included at the end of the video.

The control group received a general instruction video that was not self-made and unrelated to the topic of mobile payment. This video was about the influence of China on the internet. This video was selected because it had a comparable structure with the intervention video.

To abide the intervention effectiveness theory of K. Monsen (2017) an identical survey was sent on November 18th, three days after the 30 participants went through the intervention process. The only difference between the first and this second survey was an included audit question to check if the participant was in the experiment or control group. With this information it became able to test the effects of an intervention on people's usage of mobile payment systems. This method helped to measure the participants identically regardless of the type of intervention they have had. Conducting the research this way, a double-blind research technique

was used.

In order to have a low sampling error, a larger sample size was needed. Based on the rules of thumb the minimum sample size should have been at least 30. This is the number of participants that were invited.

Measurements

The dependent variable, continuance of mobile payment usage, was measured by asking about topics that are related to the factors that play a role in consumers' attitudes toward mobile payments. To increase the comparability and reliability of this research (Bruner, Hensel & James, 2005), the same off-the-shelf multi-item measures as ZhunZhun, Shenglin & Ruidong (2019) were used; these measures include topics as the applications that users used, in what situation they used it, how often they used it and how they felt when they used these applications.

To measure the independent variable risk-awareness, a multi-item measurement scale was created to fit the purpose of this research. These questions were formed by following the steps of the 'Guidelines for questionnaire design' (Sekaran, U. & Bougie, R., 2016). By using the Nominal Group Technique (Tague, N. 2005) in combination with the guidelines, the multi-item measurement scale was developed. Afterwards, the complete survey was tested by three individuals to validate if the questions had the desired effect.

In the second survey, after the intervention, participants received an almost identical survey to have comparable pre- and post-intervention data and prevent instrumentation effects. The only difference between the two surveys, was that the second survey contained a check-question. This check-question was unrelated to the independent or dependent variable, and was only to check if the participant watched the full video instruction.

Since both the independent and dependent variable are ratio measurement scales, the statistical technique for the analysis is a regression analysis. The data are analyzed using SPSS 26 for Windows and an alpha of 0.05 was used to determine the significant effects. By calculating Cronbach's alpha a conclusion can be drawn from the analysis. Besides that other comparing techniques will be used, looking at the models that can be drawn from the surveys.

Table 3. Measurement variables

Risk-awareness	Continuance of mobile payment usage	Statistical Technique
Ratio	Ratio	Regression analysis

Validity and reliability

The validity and reliability of the measurement items are critically considered and discussed in this section.

Validity

Based on the Research Framework on Measurement Instrument, the type of research strategy was chosen (Sekaran, U. & Bougie, R., 2016). This experimental research was formed as an ex post facto experimental design (Sekaran, U. & Bougie, R., 2016), in this design, survey research was used for both the pretest and posttest to measure participants individually. Both groups received a video instruction, instead of a real-life tutorial, to make sure that within the groups participants received the same information. To prevent testing effects, the participants did not know whether they were part of the experiment or control group. The research constructs were measured using validated multi-item scales adapted from previous studies. The questions were both off-the-self and newly developed questions. These mixed categories of questions increased the internal validity and reliability of this research (Bruner, Hensel & James, 2005).

A convenient sampling technique was used to conduct the experiment. Since this sampling technique fails in the ability to randomize, there was a lower external validity. However, the participants that did participate in this research were randomly selected to either the intervention or control group, to prevent selection bias effects. Secondly, they filled in the second survey anonymously. Because of the applied field experiment technique, the response was captured in the natural environment of the participants which increases the external validity.

Reliability

To measure the correlation between different items the Cronbach's alphas that are most important were calculated. If these are above 0.7 they are considered acceptable. In the results these values are explained in detail.

Table 2. Summary Cronbach's alpha

Included items	Cronbach's alpha before	Cronbach's alpha after
Risk-awareness users Q5 and Q9	0.854	0.789
Continuance mobile payment usage Q4 and Q12	0.381	0.842

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

From the results of the data collection we have drawn a statistical analysis and based on this we were able to report our findings.

Risk-awareness users

To measure the effect of an intervention on the awareness of users systems the survey contained 2 questions, see appendix Q5 and Q9, in which we could measure usage. In the first survey these questions had a Cronbach's alpha of 0.854 and in the second survey, after the intervention, these questions had a Cronbach's alpha of 0.789 which makes them reliable.

The results show a significant difference between risk-awareness after an intervention. The first survey conducted that the sample group had a μ of 3.14 which means that people might of might not check their mobile payment systems when connected to an unprotected connection. The survey after the interview concluded a μ of 3.75 which means that people are less likely to check their mobile payment systems when connected to an unprotected connection.

Continuance of mobile payment usage

To measure the continuance of mobile payment usage 2 questions were concluded in the survey, see appendix Q4 and Q12. In the first survey these questions had a Cronbach's alpha of 0.381 and in the second survey, after the intervention, these questions had a Cronbach's alpha of 0.842. The results of the Cronbach's alpha are inconclusive since the first survey shows inconsistency. This makes this measurement unreliable.

The first survey conducted the sample group had a μ of 1.9 which meant a few times a week. The second survey, after the intervention, showed a μ of 1.875. After controlling for gender, no significant difference was found for receiving the intervention.

Excluding other variables

To measure if other variables may have affected the results a control group was added to the experiment. After the second survey was conducted this group showed a slight change in their risk-awareness. A μ of 3.26 was measured instead of the earlier perceived 3.14. Their continuance of mobile payment usage concluded to μ 2.00 instead of the earlier perceived μ of 1.9. The results showed no significant difference between the first and second survey and so other variables are excluded.

Regression analysis

To test whether or not risk-awareness and continuance of mobile payment usage are correlated a correlation analysis was conducted. The results of the first survey showed that risk-awareness and continuance of mobile payment usage were not correlated [$r = 0.080$]. The survey after an intervention showed a negative autocorrelation [$r = -0.474$]. This means that if risk-awareness rises the continuance usage of mobile payment systems decreases.

DISCUSSION

This research sheds light on the research field concerning the effect of increasing risk awareness on the continuous usage of mobile payment systems through an intervention. Within the limitations of this research, the current study reveals that an intervention increases risk-awareness. An increase in risk-awareness was associated with a change in continuous usage of mobile payment systems. The current results indicate a negative autocorrelation, which means that an increase of the risk-awareness leads to a decrease in the continuance usage of mobile payment systems. This finding is in accordance with the study of Schilder et al (2015), and proves that an intervention on risk-awareness is applicable for the mobile payment field as well.

Since this experiment is only performed with students, performing the same experiment on a different population could provide new insights. According to CBR (2018) Dutch people between the ages from 18 to 55 are the most common digital crime victims. Conducting a similar research on a population from 25 to 55 may lead to new insights.

A noticeable factor in this research was the mortality effect that occurred between the first and

second survey. The first survey was completed by 35 people but the follow-up survey was only completed by 4 persons of the experimental group and 4 people in the control group. Even though participants were promised an incentive after the second survey, they did not seem to be motivated to continue the research. For future research, using a participatory approach could be used to prevent drop-out rates. A participatory approach is an interactive intervention that has proven its success for health interventions (Huijs, J. J. J. M., Houtman, I. L. D., Taris, T. W. & Blonk, R. W., 2019). Using a participatory approach could motivate more people to continue the experiment and be involved with the intervention.

CONCLUSION

This research has been conducted in a short amount of time and with limited resources. Some issues of this study will be critically discussed.

Limitations

The experiment was done on students of the Tilburg University (age 18-24). But this means that all the other people in the population are excluded in this sample. Therefore the conclusions of this research cannot be generalized to the whole population.

Another limitation of this research is the history effect. Since the whole experiment is performed within a week time, it is hard to determine the internal validity due to the history risks. The less frequent mobile payment intention between the interaction and the posttest might be caused by different reasons.

The validity and reliability of this study were not optimal due to the circumstances being a short amount of time and limited resources. This increases the importance to verify current outcomes through future studies. With the limitations taken into account, this research could be a starting point for future researchers when they have a wider sample and longer research time. However, the outcomes of the current study can have great practical implications.

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